

CMC Prediction for Ionic Surfactants in Pure Water and Aqueous Salt Solutions Based Solely on Tabulated Molecular Parameters

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Abstract

The critical micelle concentration (CMC) of various surfactants is difficult to predict accurately, yet often necessary to do in both industry and science. Hence, quantum-chemical software packages for precise calculation of CMC were developed, but they are expensive and time consuming. We show here an easy method for calculating CMC with a reasonable accuracy. Firstly, CMC₀ (intrinsic CMC, absent added salt) was coupled with quantitative structure – property relationship (QSPR) with defined by us parameter “CMC predictor” f_i . It can be easily calculated from a number of tabulated molecular parameters – the adsorption energy of surfactant’s head, the adsorption energy of its methylene groups, its number of carbon atoms, the specific adsorption energy of its counter-ions, their valency and bare radius. We applied this method to determine CMC₀ to a test set of 11 ionic surfactants, yielding 7.5 % accuracy. Furthermore, we calculated CMC in the presence of added salts using the advanced version of Corrin-Harkins equation, which accounts for both the intrinsic and the added counter-ions. Our salt-saturation multiplier, accounts for both the type and concentration of the added counter-ions. We applied our theory to a test set containing 11 anionic/cationic surfactant + salt systems, achieving 8% accuracy.

Keywords: Critical micelle concentration (CMC), “adsorption capacity”, adsorption energy, equilibrium adsorption constant, ion-specific effects.

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1. Introduction

An outstanding challenge in chemistry is relating the molecular structure of chemical compounds with their physical and chemical properties. Quantitative structure – property/activity relationship (QSPR/QSAR) is a scientific approach [1] consisted of relating the molecular structure of the substances with their physico-chemical properties (QSPR) or activities (QSAR). Surfactants are a special class of amphiphilic, surface-active molecules of great industrial importance, and predicting their critical micelle concentration CMC_0 (the subscript 0 refers to CMC in the absence of dissolved salts) has been both a fundamental and an applied problem. For this reason, it is not surprise that attempts to relate the surfactant's molecular structure to its CMC_0 value have been made in the literature since long time ago. Thus for example, Klevens established an empirical relation [2] between the CMC_0 value of simple surfactant and the number of carbon atoms N of its molecular tail, expressed by:

$$\log CMC_0 = A - BN \quad (1)$$

where A is a constant, which depends on the particular combination ionic head + counter-ion (for ionic surfactants) [2-5] or on the type of the polar head (for nonionic surfactants)[6], while B depends on the type of the surfactant (ionic, nonionic, zwitterionic) [6]. Equation (1) shows a simple dependence between $\log CMC_0$ and N , but unfortunately it is only valid for surfactant homologue series with simple molecular structure and with the same ionic head + counter-ion. The change of anyone of them affects the constant A .

To expand the validity of this approach to ethoxylated surfactants Ravey et al. [7] and Becher [8] derived similar relationships between $\log CMC_0$ and the numbers of carbon and the ethylene oxide groups in the molecule. Again their equations were applied to certain particular cases of surfactants. Subsequently, to generalize this approach the number of atoms only is not sufficient. The molecular geometry and other important molecular properties (e.g. dipole moment, polarizability, molecular surface area, *etc.*) could play important role here. To account more profoundly for the role of the molecular structure into the various physico-chemical properties of the organic substances molecular descriptors were introduced. They are dimensionless values (numbers), computed by special quantum chemical software packages (e.g. CODESSA[9], DRAGON[10], COSMOtherm and COSMO-RS[11]) based on input set of data of the molecular structure. Thus, the already calculated values of the molecular descriptors are used as input set of

data into special software for regression analysis, in which the physico-chemical property values of the organic substances are additionally introduced as second input data. Hence, the software establishes QSPR/QSAR polynomial correlation dependences between the two sets of input data. This QSPR/QSAR relation can predict particular physico-chemical property of the certain new organic substance once its molecular descriptors are introduced into the software. Thus, Stanton and Jurs [12, 13] introduced partial molecular charged surface area descriptors to correlate with the surface tension of number of organic liquids. Katrizky et al. [14] developed methodology with more sophisticated molecular descriptors, coded into a software (CODESSA: Comprehensive Descriptors for Structural and Statistical Analysis), and successfully correlated them with some physical properties of a number of substances. The first to develop molecular descriptors for correlation with the CMC_0 values of the surfactants were Huibers et al. [15, 16]. They faced some difficulties with correlating the CMC_0 values of some surfactants with their molecular descriptors. Fortunately the molecular descriptors underwent development [11, 17-20] thus enormously enlarging the predictive power of the QSPR method. Nowadays QSPR [17-19] and QSAR[20-22] are powerful methods predicting various properties of the substances due to the significant development of the quantum chemistry and its molecular descriptors. Nowadays these methods have been applied for calculation of the surfactant's hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB)[21], cloud point [22], solubility [23, 24], cleaning effect [25], toxicity[26], vapor pressure [27] *etc.* The distinction QSPR/QSAR regards mostly the general physicochemical macro-properties of the molecules (QSPR) or their activity for specific applications (QSAR). To conduct all these calculations, one should be well knowledgeable in molecular and quantum mechanics. This work aims to relief the calculation of CMC_0 , thus making it easy for everyone. A new surfactant's molecular descriptor, called "adsorption capacity" was introduced recently [28, 29]. It is based on the molecular structure of the surfactant and tabulated data on the energy of adsorption of the most common in the literature surfactant's hydrophilic heads and corresponding counter-ions on air/water interface. It was shown that this new parameter can be used for easy and independent of any adsorption model calculation of the equilibrium adsorption constant of the ionic surfactants with simple molecular structure (see the Suppl. Material). This work introduces a modification on the previously calculated parameter "adsorption capacity" to obtain a new molecular descriptor called a "CMC predictor", which allows for easy calculation of the intrinsic values CMC_0 of ionic surfactants. The "CMC predictor" is based on the former

parameter “adsorption capacity” [28, 29] and the radius of the surfactant’s bare counter-ion and its valency. We present here a QSPR method for easy determination of the intrinsic value CMC_0 of surfactants based on calculated values of the “CMC predictor”, and known parameters of the counter-ion and electrolyte salts. This simplified relationship avoids the time-consuming conventional QSPR procedures for calculation of CMC_0 . We used a training set of 13 ionic surfactants to establish polynomial QSPR relation between the “CMC predictor” and the CMC_0 value of the surfactants. Furthermore, we test the accuracy of the method against an experimental data with a set of 11 ionic surfactants with known values of intrinsic CMC_0 . Note for all the equations and plots involving logarithms, we have used the value of CMC in mM units, dividing by 1 mM to make them dimensionless.

Researchers also often need not only the intrinsic value of the CMC in the absence of salts, but also in their presence, and ion-specific effects can be significant. Recent models for such calculations[30-33] are all based on the thermodynamic semi-empirical approach of Corrin-Harkins[34, 35]. This approach in its original form, unfortunately, has four general drawbacks: (i) the intrinsic value CMC_0 is an unknown constant that should be determined first; (ii) there is no account for the known ion-specific differences of various salts (iii) there is an empirical unknown constant K_g representing the fraction of surfactant head-group ions from the micelle, which is bound with counter-ions; The latter is a number between zero and one. (iv) the concentration of the added salt should be significantly larger than the intrinsic value CMC_0 of the surfactant. Fortunately, recent improvements [36, 37] have included ion-specific effects, and established that K_g is a number close to 1/2. Consequently, one could assume $K_g = 1/2$ in the first approximation. Therefore, the intrinsic value CMC_0 is the only unknown parameter in the new Corrin-Harkins equation [36, 37]. Hence, if the value of CMC_0 is obtained by means of the QSPR approach, one could be able to calculate easily the new value of CMC upon the addition of salt. We suggest with this work a new advanced version of Corrin-Harkins equation accounting for the specific effect of the counter-ions of the added salt on the value of CMC. Moreover, it accounts for both the surfactant’s intrinsic counter-ions and these ones of the added salt. We established that the K_g value depends on the type of the ionic surfactant (anionic or cationic), the type of the added salt and its concentration. For this reason we developed a new value accounting for the type of the added salt and its concentration. We called this value salt-saturation multiplier. The

dependences between the values of K_g and the salt-saturation multiplier differ for cases of anionic and cationic surfactants. We used training sets of 7 cationic systems (cationic surfactants + different added salts) and 9 anionic systems (anionic surfactant + different added salts) to establish empirical dependences between K_g and the value of the salt-saturation multiplier for the cases of anionic and cationic surfactants. Thus, we applied the new version of Corrin-Harkins equation in this work to a test series of 11 surfactant/salt combinations with known CMC with 8% accuracy.

Overall, we present here a QSPR method for the easy determination of the intrinsic value CMC_0 of surfactants based on calculated values of “CMC predictor”, and known parameters of the counter-ion and electrolyte salts. Moreover, we show procedure for calculation of CMC in presence of salt via advanced version of Corrin-Harkins equation. Both procedures calculate the values of CMC with satisfactory accuracy.

2. Theory

We will show hereafter the theoretical basis of our approach. Firstly, we will focus on the intrinsic value of the CMC and its relation with the “adsorption capacity” and the “CMC predictor”. Afterward, we will present the advanced equation of Corrin-Harkins, by which one can calculate the CMC of surfactant upon addition of salt. Both theories are presented in details in the supplementary material.

2.1. QSPR approach, intrinsic value CMC_0 , “adsorption capacity” and “CMC predictor”

A polynomial regression of second order of QSPR modelling method can be presented in the following way[38]:

$$\ln CMC_0 = a_{00} + a_{11}x_1 + a_{22}x_1^2 + a_{33}x_2 + a_{44}x_2^2 + a_{55}x_3 + a_{66}x_3^2 + \dots \quad (2),$$

where x_1 , x_2 , x_3 ..., are molecular descriptors, while a_{00} , a_{11} , a_{22} , a_{33} , a_{44} , a_{55} are fitting coefficients. As mentioned above, to calculate the molecular descriptors is meticulous, long and expensive procedure. For this reason, we aim at replacing these descriptors with only one, which can be calculated easily and fast. Eq. (2) can be presented in the following way:

$$\ln CMC_0 = a_{00} + a_{11}f_1 + a_{22}f_1^2 \quad (3),$$

where f_1 is ‘‘CMC predictor’’ of the ionic surfactant. The ‘‘CMC predictor’’ can be calculated by means of the following relation:

$$f_1 = f_0 + \frac{r_b}{3} [H(a_1 - r_b)H(z) + H(a_2 - r_b)H(-z)] \quad (4),$$

where $H(x)$ is Heaviside step function, r_b is the bare radius of the surfactant’s counter-ion, z is its valency, $a_1 = 0.7$, $a_2 = 1.65$. A key parameter in Eq. (4) is the parameter ‘‘adsorption capacity’’ f_0 , which is related with the equilibrium adsorption constant and consequently to the molecular structure of the surfactant.

The ‘‘adsorption capacity’’ f_0 can be presented by the following equation (see the supplementary material):

$$f_0 = \ln K - \tilde{b} = \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{E_{head}}{k_B T} + \frac{u_{CH_2}}{k_B T} (N + 1) \right) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{u_0}{k_B T} + \frac{1}{3} \ln \frac{4}{\kappa_0^2} \quad (5)$$

$$\tilde{b} = \frac{1}{3} \left(\ln \delta_s + \frac{\sigma_0 \alpha_{\perp}}{k_B T} \right)$$

where K is equilibrium adsorption constant of the ionic surfactant, $E_{head}/k_B T$ is the dimensionless energy of adsorption of the hydrophilic heads of the surfactant molecule on air/water interface, $u_{CH_2}/k_B T$ is the dimensionless energy of adsorption of one methylene group from the surfactant’s hydrocarbon tail, N is the number of carbon atoms into the surfactant hydrocarbon’s tail, $u_0/k_B T$ is dimensionless specific energy of adsorption of the counter-ions,

$\kappa_0 = \sqrt{8\pi e^2 / \varepsilon k_B T}$ is the inverted Debye length excluding concentration, e is the charge of one electron (in CGS system), and ε is the dielectric constant of the solution, k_b is Boltzmann constant (in CGS system), T is absolute temperature, $\delta_s = l_{CH_2} / \frac{u_{CH_2}}{k_B T}$ is adsorption length,

$l_{CH_2} = 0.126\text{nm}$ is the length of one CH_2 group, $\sigma_0 \alpha_{\perp} / k_B T$ is the adsorption energy gained due to the displacing of surface water molecules by one surfactant molecule, σ_0 is the surface tension of the free air/water interface, and $\alpha_{\perp} = 0.21\text{nm}^2$ is the approximate cross-sectional area occupied by one single surfactant molecule on air/water interface. The parameter \tilde{b} in Eq. (5) remain a constant despite the kind of the surfactant molecule with error of about 1.5% [28, 29]. For this

reason we do not need to calculate \tilde{b} for each particular case when we want to estimate the “adsorption capacity” of given surfactant. In Eq. (5) $\ln(4/\kappa_0^2)/3 = 4.873$ (T=293.15K). The “adsorption capacity” is a measure of the surface activity of the ionic surfactant. We must stress here that Eqs. (4) and (5) are valid only for surfactants with simple molecular structure – hydrocarbon tail ending with a hydrophilic charged head and its corresponding counter-ion. The adsorption energy of the hydrophilic head $E_{head}/k_B T$ is often unknown parameter. However, we have recently shown[28] how to determine this parameter. Moreover, we have determined the energy of adsorption of eight hydrophilic heads on air/water interface [28] and their corresponding energies of adsorption of the individual methylene groups CH₂ (see the supplementary material). Moreover, we have determined the specific energy of counter-ion adsorption on air/water interface for a number of cations and anions.

Hence, one can calculate the “CMC predictor” of every kind simple surfactant molecules with known number of carbon atoms, and known adsorption energy of the hydrophilic head.

2.2. Advanced Corrin-Harkins equation accounting for the ion-specific effects [36, 37] (see the supplementary material).

The original Corrin-Harkins equation [34, 35] can be expressed in the following form:

$$\ln \text{CMC} = B_{(const)} - K_g \ln(\text{CMC} + C_{el}) \quad (6),$$

where CMC is the critical micelle concentration of ionic surfactant in presence of added salt with concentration C_{el} , K_g is empirical constant ($0 < K_g < 1$) [30, 34] expressing the degree of binding of the surfactant monomers from the micelle with the counter-ions, and $B_{(const)}$ is an empirical constant. Ivanov et al. [36] extended Eq.(6) in a new form, thus including the effect of the type the counter-ions on CMC (see the supplementary material). The new equation was obtained by means of equality of the chemical potentials of the monomers from the solution and these ones from the micelles. The electrical contribution to the chemical potential of the monomers from the micelles was accounted for. The counter-ion binding is accounted for by means of the empirical constant K_g . The van der Waals contribution of the counter-ions was included by means of the Gouy equation to account for the specific adsorption energy of the

counter-ions on air/water interface. The latter was incorporated into the equation about the equality of the chemical potentials. Finally, the following general equation of Corrin-Harkins was obtained:

$$\ln \text{CMC} = (1 + K_g) \ln C_0 - K_g \ln (\text{CMC} + C_{el}) + \frac{K_g u_0}{k_B T} \quad (7),$$

where C_0 is standard critical micelle concentration (CMC) with excluded ion-specific effect.

One can see that if we neglect the specific energy of adsorption of the counter-ions ($u_0 / k_B T = 0$), we arrive at the classical equation of Corrin-Harkins, but with determined empirical constant (see Eq.(6)):

$$\ln \text{CMC} = (1 + K_g) \ln C_0 - K_g \ln (\text{CMC} + C_{el}) \quad (8)$$

Eq. (7) can be presented in the following form:

$$\ln \text{CMC} = \ln C_0 - \frac{K_g}{(1 + K_g)} \left(-\frac{u_0}{k_B T} + \ln \left(1 + \frac{C_{el}}{\text{CMC}} \right) \right) \quad (9)$$

The intrinsic value of the critical micelle concentration CMC_0 can be presented as follows:

$$\ln \text{CMC}_0 = \ln C_0 + \frac{K_g}{(1 + K_g)} \frac{u_0}{k_B T} \quad (10),$$

Hence, Eq. (9) can be expressed as follows:

$$\ln \text{CMC} = \ln \text{CMC}_0 - \frac{K_g}{(1 + K_g)} \ln \left(1 + \frac{C_{el}}{\text{CMC}} \right) \quad (11)$$

Eq.(11) is valid for the case of surfactant ions + only one type of counter-ions (e.g. SDS + NaCl), i.e. the added counter-ions by means of salt are identical to the intrinsic ones. This equation has been applied in the case of a mixture of two types [37] of counter-ions, but with great excess of one of them. Unfortunately the latter case is particular. In most of the cases the added salt is not in great excess and we need more general equation to calculate CMC.

After careful analysis, we arrived at the following equation:

$$\ln \text{CMC} = \ln \text{CMC}_0^{(\text{int})} \frac{\text{CMC}}{\text{CMC} + C_{el}} + \ln \text{CMC}_0^{(\text{new})} \frac{C_{el}}{\text{CMC} + C_{el}} - \frac{K_g}{(1 + K_g)} \ln \left(1 + \frac{C_{el}}{\text{CMC}} \right) \quad (12),$$

where $CMC_0^{(int)}$ and $CMC_0^{(new)}$ are the CMC of the surfactant with the intrinsic and the newly added counter ions. For example, for the case of SDS + KCl, $CMC_0^{(int)}$ regards CMC of SDS, while $CMC_0^{(new)}$ regards KDS.

The intrinsic values $CMC_0^{(int)}$ and $CMC_0^{(new)}$ are unknown parameters here, but we determined them by means of the above mentioned simplified version of QSPR method. Conclusively, we suggest self-consistent procedure for calculation of the CMC of simple ionic surfactants with heads, whose adsorption energy has been determined preliminary (see the supplementary material).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. QSPR procedure for calculation the intrinsic CMC_0 value of ionic surfactants

We will begin this section with a brief validation of Kleven's equation (see Eq. (1)). As far as this equation can be applied successfully only to a homologue series of surfactants with both identical ionic head and counter-ion we choose two homologue series – anionic $C_nH_{2n+1}SO_4Na$ and cationic $C_nH_{2n+1}N(CH_3)_3Br$.

Figure 1. $\log CMC_0$ versus the number of methylene groups in the surfactant's hydrocarbon tail for two homologous series: anionic $C_nH_{2n+1}SO_4Na$ and cationic $C_nH_{2n+1}N(CH_3)_3Br$.

Shown in Fig. 1 is the dependence of $\log CMC_0$ on the number of methylene groups for $C_nH_{2n+1}SO_4Na$ and $C_nH_{2n+1}N(CH_3)_3Br$ homologue series. The linear dependence within the limits

of each of the surfactant homologue series is reproduced well by the Klevens equation (Eq. 1). Moreover, one can see that the slopes of the theoretical lines in Fig. 1 are close to -0.3 , which is typical for ionic surfactants [6]. As mentioned before, the Klevens equation is applicable only for surfactant homologue series with the same head and counter ion. We aim to introduce a more general equation, which can be applied to surfactants with single hydrocarbon tail with different ionic heads and counter-ions.

The “CMC predictor”, which was described in the previous section, was derived in its present form only for simple ionic surfactants – one hydrocarbon tail ending with a hydrophilic charged head and corresponding counter-ion with known (tabulated) values of their energies of adsorption on air/water interface. For this reason, we have started with a number of surfactants with simple molecular structure, thus validating our approach. The same approach can be applied to surfactants with more complicated molecular structure if their “adsorption capacities” are determined.

We have used the experimental intrinsic values of 13 ionic surfactants (see Suppl. Table 3) and calculated their “CMC predictors”. The literature data about the intrinsic values of CMC_0 are taken from surface tension isotherms of the surfactants. After this we have made polynomial fitting (QSPR dependence) of $\ln CMC_0$ versus the values of the “CMC predictors” (see Fig. 2). Shown in Fig. 2 is the dependence of $\ln CMC_0$ on the value of the “CMC predictor” f_1 , of all the surfactants from the training set (see Suppl. Table 3).

The experimental points were fitted with the polynomial of the second order. The training set of surfactants can be described by the following polynomial of the second order:

$$\ln CMC_0 = 0.1151f_1^2 - 3.8367f_1 + 28.158 \quad (13)$$

After this we applied the established QSPR dependence Eq. (13) to another test set with 11 ionic surfactants with known intrinsic values of CMC_0 (see Table 1 and Fig. 3).

Shown in Table 1 are the surfactants from the test set, their “adsorption capacities”, their “CMC predictors” and the corresponding experimental QSPR values of CMC_0 . The average precision for this calculation is about 7.5% as compared to the experimental data.

One can see in Fig. 3 $\ln CMC_0$ of the surfactants from the test set (see Table 2) calculated by means of our QSPR procedure versus $\ln CMC_0$ taken from the literature’s experimental data.

The values of the slope (close to unity) and the intercept (close to zero) indicate remarkable overall agreement between theoretical and experimental data.

Table 1. Surfactants, their “adsorption capacity” f_0 , “CMC predictor” f_1 , experimental CMC_0 and QSPR (predicted) values of CMC_0 of the test set of the ionic surfactants.

No	Surfactant	f_0	f_1	CMC_0 (experiment) mM	CMC_0 (QSPR), mM
1	$C_7H_{15}SO_4Na$ [39]	7.47	7.47	385.44	374.87
2	$C_8H_{17}COOK$ [40]	7.78	7.78	200.00	197.26
3	$C_8H_{17}N(CH_3)_3Br$ [41]	7.57	7.57	290.00	306.50
4	$C_{12}H_{25}NH_3Cl$ [42]	8.75	9.30	13.80	11.45
5	$C_{12}H_{25}N(C_3H_7)_3Br$ [43]	9.49	9.49	8.50	8.36
6	$C_{12}H_{25}SO_4Na$ [44]	9.57	9.57	8.39	7.31
7	$C_{12}H_{25}SO_4K$ [45]	9.68	9.68	6.71	6.16
8	$C_{12}H_{25}SO_4Rb$ [45]	9.71	9.71	5.90	5.78
9	$C_{12}H_{25}N(C_3H_7)_4Br$ [43]	9.87	9.87	4.50	4.49
10	$C_{14}H_{29}SO_4Na$ [39]	10.41	10.41	2.05	2.01
11	$C_{16}H_{33}N(CH_3)_3Br$ [46]	10.77	10.77	0.95	1.21

Figure 2. The experimental $LnCMC_0$ versus the “CMC predictor” of the ionic surfactant from the training set.

Figure 3. LnCMC₀ (QSPR) versus LnCMC₀ (experimental) of the test set of surfactants.

3.2. Procedure for calculation of CMC value of ionic surfactant upon addition of salt by means of advanced version of Corrin-Harkins equation

Once we determine the intrinsic values CMC₀ of ionic surfactants, we can use the advanced equation of Corrin-Harkins (Eq.(12)) to calculate the values of CMC upon addition of salts. This model considers micelles with two types of counter-ions: the intrinsic one and the added one. Thus, we have calculated the intrinsic value CMC₀ of the ionic surfactant with the new (added) counter-ions and with the intrinsic counter-ions originally belonging to the ionic surfactant. The only unknown parameter in this equation remains the counter-ion binding parameter K_g , which we know has a value close to 1/2. [36, 37] The experimental values of CMC have been determined in the literature mainly by means of the conductometric and the calorimetric methods [47]. The average difference between the values of CMC (conductometric) and CMC (calorimetric) is about 8.5 %. For this reason, we have operated with the averaged experimental values of CMC, thus aiming at the deviation of the theoretical values of CMC from the averaged experimental ones less than 8%

We applied the advanced equation of Corrin-Harkins (Eq.(12)) to training sets of 7 cationic systems (cationic surfactants + different added salts) and 9 anionic systems (anionic surfactant + different added salts). The parameter K_g was considered 1/2 in the first

approximation and afterwards was adjusted additionally until we achieved coincidence between the averaged experimental and the theoretical values of CMC with precision better than the experimental error (8.5%). Furthermore, by analysis of the thus obtained values of K_g we have been led to the further conclusion that the counter-ion binding fraction K_g depends on both the concentration of the added salt and the type of its counter-ions in contrast to the case of micelles with only one (intrinsic) type of counter-ions, at which K_g does not depend on the salt concentration. We have defined a dimensionless parameter characterizing each one of the systems (surfactant + added salt), which we named salt-saturation multiplier:

$$\xi = -\frac{C_{el}}{CMC_0^{(int)}} \frac{u_0}{k_B T} \quad (14),$$

where C_{el} is the concentration of the added salt, $CMC_0^{(int)}$ is the intrinsic value of CMC in the absence of added salt, and $u_0 / k_B T$ is specific adsorption energy of the counter-ions of the added salt. The parameter ξ accounts for the intrinsic value CMC_0 of the surfactant, the concentration of added salt and nature of the added counter-ion by means of the added salt. We call this factor for simplicity salt-saturation multiplier

Figure 4. Dependence of the degree of counter-ion binding K_g on the value of salt saturation multiplier ξ of training set (empty points), and the test set (cross points) (see Table 2, and Suppl.

Table 5) of the system anionic surfactant + added salt. For simplicity the data is also fitted with two linear dependencies, Eq. (15).

Figure 5. Dependence of the degree of counter-ion binding K_g on the value of a salt saturation multiplier ξ of the training set (empty points) test set (cross points) of the system cationic surfactants + added salts; (see Table 2, and Suppl. Table 5); For simplicity the data is also fitted with two linear dependencies Eq. (16).

Shown in Figs. 4 and 5 are the dependencies of the K_g on the parameter ξ for the training sets of anionic and cationic systems. The shapes of the curves in Figs. 4 and 5 remind us of adsorption curves of surfactants vs. their concentration. It is not surprising, since K_g is a counter-ion binding parameter quantifying the adsorption of the layer of counter-ions bound to the surfactant head group ions in the micelle.

Once these adsorption-like dependencies were established (see Figs. 4 and 5 and Eqs. (15) and (16)) we applied them to another test set of corresponding anionic and cationic systems. The calculated values of K_g are signified with cross points in Figs. 4 and 5. One can see that K_g increases significantly upon the increase of ξ until reaching a certain value, beyond which the further increase of K_g is substantially weaker.

The dependencies of K_g on ξ thus found were approximated with the line equation (see Figs. 4 and 5) expressed by:

For anionic surfactants:

$$\begin{aligned} K_g &= 0.24\xi + 0.2669 + 0.22H(N-17) \quad \text{for } 0.1 \leq \xi \leq 1.3 \\ K_g &= 0.0026\xi + 0.6075 + 0.22H(N-17) \quad \text{for } 1.3 \leq \xi \end{aligned} \quad (15),$$

For a cationic surfactants:

$$\begin{aligned} K_g &= 0.0559\xi + 0.1061 + 0.22H(N-17) \quad \text{for } 0.3 \leq \xi \leq 8 \\ K_g &= 0.0002\xi + 0.7044 + 0.22H(N-17) \quad \text{for } 10 \leq \xi \end{aligned} \quad (16),$$

where $H(x)$ is Heaviside function, and N is the number of the carbon atoms into the surfactant's hydrocarbon tail.

One can see in Figs. 4 and 5 additionally fixed adsorption-like curves following the basic trends.

We applied the modified Langmuir adsorption isotherm to fit the K_g vs. ξ dependence:

$$K_g = \frac{ab\xi^p}{1+b\xi^p} \quad (17),$$

where a has a meaning of maximal adsorption fraction of the counter-ions onto the charged head groups of the surfactants ions from the micelle (number between zero and one), b is their dimensionless equilibrium adsorption constant, and p is dimensionless parameter accounting for the strength of the counter-ion – surfactant's head group bond. One can see that the equilibrium adsorption constant of the cations on negatively charged micelles is almost an order of magnitude higher than this one of anions on the positively charged micelles, while the strength of the bonds is smaller in the first case as compared to the second case.

We have used Eqs. (15)(16) to calculate the values of K_g of two test sets of anionic and cationic systems containing totally 11 combinations of ionic surfactants + added salts. Hence, we solved the advanced version of Corrin-Harkins equation (Eq.(12) to obtain the values of CMC of each member of the test sets. The average deviation between the experimental (averaged) and the thus obtained theoretical value of CMC was found to be about 8 %.

Shown in Fig. 6 is the dependence of the theoretically determined LnCMC from the test sets of the anionic and cationic systems versus the averaged experimental values of LnCMC. One can see the very good agreement between theoretical and experimental data.

Figure 6. LnCMC (Theoretical) from the test sets of anionic and cationic systems obtained in the present work, versus LnCMC (averaged experimental).

Table 2 presents the systems (ionic surfactant + added salt) from the test sets, their experimental and theoretical values of CMC, and the corresponding values of ξ and K_g . One can see that in most of the cases the theoretical values of CMC is close to the experimental ones despite being measured by means of conductometry or calorimetry.

Our procedure looks restricted as far as it is valid only for simple ionic surfactants ending with a limited number of hydrophilic charged heads, which can be combined with the limited number of counter-ions. However, if we assume all the ionic surfactants with one hydrocarbon chain with the number of carbon atoms between one and sixteen, combined with the already tabulated hydrophilic charged heads and counter-ions we can count 480 different surfactants, whose “adsorption capacity” can be calculated by means of our procedure. The latter allows us to calculate their equilibrium adsorption constants and intrinsic values CMC_0 .

This allows us to calculate CMC of thousands of systems, ionic surfactant + added salt.

Table 2. Surfactants + added salt systems from the test sets and their experimental and theoretical values of CMC, and corresponding ξ and K_g ; the abbreviations “Cond.” and “Cal.” mean experimental values of CMC determined by conductometry and calorimetry.

No	System	CMC(Expt.) mM (Cond.)	CMC(Expt.) mM(Cal.)	CMC(Theor.) mM	ξ	K_g
1	C ₁₂ H ₂₅ SO ₄ Na + 15 mM LiClO ₄ [48]	5.60	-	5.88	0.18	0.32
2	C ₁₂ H ₂₅ SO ₄ Na + 15 mM NaCl [30]	4.51	-	4.99	0.66	0.43
3	C ₁₂ H ₂₅ SO ₄ Na + 10 mM NH ₄ Cl [47]	4.24	4.58	4.26	0.81	0.46
4	C ₁₂ H ₂₅ SO ₄ Na + 25 mM NaCl [30]	3.42	4.17	3.55	1.10	0.53
5	C ₁₂ H ₂₅ SO ₄ Na + 15 mM NH ₄ ClO ₄ [48]	3.50	-	3.27	1.22	0.56
6	C ₁₂ H ₂₅ SO ₄ Na + 50 mM NaCl [30]	-	2.33	2.19	2.19	0.61
7	C ₁₂ H ₂₅ SO ₄ Na + 100 mM NaCl [30]	-	1.72	1.43	4.38	0.62
8	C ₁₂ H ₂₅ SO ₄ Na + 800 mM NaCl [30]	-	0.30	0.27	35.08	0.70
9	C ₁₂ H ₂₅ N(CH ₃) ₃ Br + 2 mM NaBr [30]	14.40	-	13.42	0.34	0.13
10	C ₁₄ H ₂₉ N(CH ₃) ₃ Br + 10 mM NaBr [47]	1.85	2.02	2.24	6.13	0.45
11	C ₁₄ H ₂₉ N(CH ₃) ₃ Br + 10 mM NaN ₃ [47]	1.63	1.92	1.64	7.74	0.54

Our procedure can be expanded to more complicated surfactants (e.g. double chained surfactants, containing benzene ring, etc.) by means of extending our theory for the calculation of the “absorption capacity” to more complicated molecules.

5. Conclusions

An easy two-steps procedure for calculation of CMC of simple ionic surfactants has been developed.

The first step calculates the intrinsic value CMC₀ of the ionic surfactants. It operates with one molecular descriptor named “CMC predictor”, which can be easily calculated by tabulated molecular parameters of different fragments of the molecular structure of simple ionic surfactants [28, 29] (see the supplementary material). For comparison, the conventional methods for

calculation of CMC_0 of surfactants operate with numerous molecular descriptors [11, 16, 18, 49, 50] coupled with heavy and time consuming quantum-chemical calculations (see Fig.7).

Figure 7. Comparison of the classical approach for calculation of CMC_0 with the procedure proposed in this manuscript.

Shown in Fig. 7 is a comparison of the conventional way for calculation of the surfactant's CMC_0 with this one suggested here.

The short description of the first step of our procedure includes:

1. Calculation of the parameter “adsorption capacity” by means of Eq. (5) using pre-tabulated values (see our supplementary material), of adsorption energies of the surfactant's hydrophilic head and related adsorption energy per methylene group, the specific energy of counter-ion adsorption, and the number of carbon atoms into the surfactant's molecule;
2. Calculation of the “CMC predictor” by means of Eq. (4) using the value of the “adsorption capacity” f_0 and the bare radius of the surfactant's counter-ions;
3. Calculation of the intrinsic value CMC_0 of the surfactant by means of QSPR polynomial Eq. (3) using the value of the “CMC predictor” f_1 .

The second step calculates the value of CMC in presence of added salt. It uses a new advanced version of the Corrin-Harkins equation. In contrast to the previous versions of Corrin-Harkins equations[34, 36, 37, 51], this one accounts for the contributions of both the intrinsic and the added counter-ions. A short description of our calculation procedure is presented in the supplementary material.

The procedure for easy prediction of CMC will contribute for improving of the understanding about the molecular parameters, which are the mostly important for the micellization, and other properties reported in the literature [11, 16, 18, 49, 50].

A promising future direction of our work would be generalizing our procedure by adapting it to surfactants with more complicated molecular structure, thus extending the scope for significantly larger number of surfactants.

Acknowledgment: The work was funded through the European Research Council (ERC) grant EMATTER #280078. We thank Prof. Denkov and Prof. Tcholakova for the supply of $C_{18}H_{37}N(CH_3)_3Br$. Stoyan Karakashev thanks the H2020 Project Materials Networking for financial support. We thank Dr. N. Grozev for his invaluable help for the experimental determination of CMC of $C_{18}H_{37}N(CH_3)_3Br$.

Nomenclature

Latin letters

A – Constant in the Klevens equation responsible for the intercept of the linear trend;

a_{11}, a_{22}, \dots – Coefficients into the main QSPR polynomial dependence;

a – A constant in Langmuir equation applied to the relation between K_g and ξ ;

a_{\perp} – Cross-sectional area of one surfactant molecule on air/water interface;

$a_1 = 0.7$ – Correction coefficient for cationic counter-ions in the Heaviside step function;
 $a_2 = 1.65$ – Correction coefficient for anionic counter-ions in the Heaviside step function;
 B – Constant in the Klevens equation responsible for the slope of the linear trend;
 $B_{(const)}$ – A constant in the Corrin-Harkins equation;
 b – A constant in Langmuir equation applied to the relation between K_g and ξ ;
 \tilde{b} – A coefficient into the expression for the “adsorption capacity”;
 C_{el} – Concentration of added salt;
 CMC_0 – Intrinsic critical micelle concentration of the surfactant;
 $\ln CMC_0^{(new)}$ – Critical micelle concentration of surfactant with the counter-ions of the added salt;
 $\ln CMC_0^{(int)}$ – Critical micelle concentration of surfactant with its intrinsic counter-ions (with no added salt);
 CMC – Critical micelle concentration of the surfactant in presence of added salt;
 E_A – Adsorption energy;
 e – Charge of one electron;
 f_0 – Adsorption capacity;
 f_1 – CMC predictor;
 K – Equilibrium adsorption constant of charged surfactant with included contribution from the counter-ions;
 K_g – Counter-ion binding coefficient;
 r_b – Radius of bare counter-ions;
 z – Valency of the counter-ions;
 k_B – Boltzmann constant;
 l_{CH_2} – Length of one methylene group from the surfactant’s hydrocarbon tail;

N – Number of carbon atoms in the hydrocarbon tail of the surfactant;

p – Parameter of strength of counter-ion – micelle bond;

T – Absolute temperature;

u_{CH_2} – Adsorption energy of one methylene group from the surfactant's hydrocarbon tail;

Greek letters

δ_s – Adsorption length;

ε – Dielectric permittivity of water in CGS system;

κ_0 – Inverted Debye length with excluded concentration.

σ_0 – Surface tension of pure water;

π – Number pi;

ξ – Salt saturation multiplier;

5. References

- [1] B. Zoe, in: (Ed.)^(Eds.); Maney publishing, London, 2005.
- [2] H.B. Klevens, *Journal of the American Oil Chemists Society* 30 (2) (1953) 74-80
- [3] Z.N. Markina, *Kolloid Zh.* 26 (76) (1964)
- [4] M.J. Rosen, 56, 320 (1976). *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 56 (2) (1976) 320
- [5] M.J. Schick, F.M. Fowkes, *J. Phys. Chem.* 61 (8) (1957) 1062-1068
- [6] M.J. Rosen, *Surfactants and Interfacial Phenomena*. Third ed., Wiley, New York, 2004.
- [7] J.C. Ravey, A. Gherbi, M.J. Stebe, in: V. Degiorgio, (Ed.)^(Eds.)*Trends in Colloid and Interface Science II*; Steinkopff, Darmstadt, 1988, p 234-241.
- [8] P. Becher, *J. Dispersion Sci. Technol.* 5 (1) (1984) 81-96
- [9] M. Karelson, U. Maran, Y.L. Wang, A.R. Katritzky, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.* 64 (10) (1999) 1551-1571
- [10] A. Mauri, V. Consonni, M. Pavan, R. Todeschini, *MATCH-Commun. Math. Co.* 56 (2) (2006) 237-248
- [11] U. Preiss, C. Jungnickel, J. Thoeming, I. Krossing, J. Luczak, M. Diedenhofen, A. Klamt, *Chem. Eur. J.* 15 (35) (2009) 8880-8885
- [12] D.T. Stanton, P.C. Jurs, *Analytical Chemistry* 62 (21) (1990) 2323-2329
- [13] D.T. Stanton, P.C. Jurs, *Journal of Chemical Information and Computer Sciences* 32 (1) (1992) 109-115
- [14] A.R. Katritzky, V.S. Lobanov, M. Karelson, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 24 (4) (1995) 279-287
- [15] P.D.T. Huibers, V.S. Lobanov, A.R. Katritzky, D.O. Shah, M. Karelson, *Langmuir* 12 (6) (1996) 1462-1470
- [16] P.D.T. Huibers, V.S. Lobanov, A.R. Katritzky, D.O. Shah, M. Karelson, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 187 (1) (1997) 113-120
- [17] A.R. Katritzky, L.M. Pacureanu, S.H. Slavov, D.A. Dobchev, M. Karelson, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 47 (23) (2008) 9687-9695
- [18] A.R. Katritzky, L.M. Pacureanu, S.H. Slavov, D.A. Dobchev, D.O. Shah, M. Karelson, *Comput. Chem. Eng* 33 (1) (2009) 321-332
- [19] M. Jalali-Heravi, E. Konouz, *J Surfactants Deterg.* 6 (1) (2003) 25-30
- [20] Z.W. Wang, G.Z. Li, X.Y. Zhang, R.K. Wang, A.J. Lou, *Coll. Surf. A* 197 (1-3) (2002) 37-45
- [21] M.-L. Chen, Z.-W. Wang, G.-X. Zhang, W.-D. Wang, Z.-N. Wang, *Acta Chim. Sinica* 65 (13) (2007) 1265-1272
- [22] M.-l. Chen, Z.-w. Wang, G.-x. Zhang, J. Gu, Z. Cun, F.-m. Tao, *Chem. Res. Chinese U.* 23 (6) (2007) 715-719
- [23] J. Ghasemi, A. Abdolmaleki, S. Asadpour, S. Fereshteh, *QSAR Comb.Sci.* 27 (3) (2008) 338-346
- [24] J. Ghasemi, S. Saaidpour, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.* 55 (4) (2007) 669-674
- [25] A. Lindgren, M. Sjostrom, S. Wold, *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.* 73 (7) (1996) 863-875
- [26] Å. Lindgren, M. Sjöström, S. Wold, *Quant. Struct.-Act. Relat.* 15 (3) (1996) 208-218
- [27] A.R. Katritzky, S.H. Slavov, D.A. Dobchev, M. Karelson, *Comput. Chem. Eng.* 31 (9) (2007) 1123-1130
- [28] S.I. Karakashev, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 432 (2014) 98-104
- [29] S.I. Karakashev, S.K. Smoukov, *Coll. Surf. A* 467 (2015) 143-148
- [30] B. Naskar, A. Dey, S.P. Moulik, *J. Surfactants Deterg.* 16 (5) (2013) 785-794

- [31] R. Nagarajan, E. Ruckenstein, *Langmuir* 7 (12) (1991) 2934-2969
- [32] L. Ambrosone, R. Ragone, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 205 (2) (1998) 454-458
- [33] P. Palladino, R. Ragone, *Langmuir* 27 (23) (2011) 14065-14070
- [34] M.L. Corrin, W.D. Harkins, *JACS* 69 (3) (1947) 683-688
- [35] K. Shinoda, T. Nakagawa, B.-I. Tamamushi, T. Isemuta, *Colloidal Surfactants, Some Physicochemical Properties*. Academic Press, New York and London, 1963.
- [36] I.B. Ivanov, R.I. Slavchov, E.S. Basheva, D. Sidzhakova, S.I. Karakashev, *Adv Colloid Interface Sci* 168 (1-2) (2011) 93-104
- [37] R.I. Slavchov, S.I. Karakashev, I.B. Ivanov, in: L.S. Romsted, (Ed.)^(Eds.) *Surfactant Science and Technology: Retrospects and Prospects*; Taylor & Francis Group, 2014, p 593.
- [38] H.H. Le, X.T. Hoang, A. Das, U. Gohs, K.W. Stoeckelhuber, R. Boldt, G. Heinrich, R. Adhikari, H.J. Radusch, *Carbon* 50 (12) (2012) 4543-4556
- [39] K. Lunkenheimer, G. Czichocki, R. Hirte, W. Barzyk, *Coll. Surf. A* 101 (2-3) (1995) 187-197
- [40] D.K. Chattoraj, K.S. Birdi, *Adsorption and the Gibbs Surface Excess*. Plenum Press, New York and London, 1984.
- [41] R. Zana, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 78 (2) (1980) 330-337
- [42] R. Vandenberg, P. Joos, *J. Phys. Chem.* 84 (2) (1980) 190-194
- [43] G. Para, A. Hamerska-Dudra, K.A. Wilk, P. Warszynski, *Coll. Surf. A* 365 (1-3) (2010) 215-221
- [44] J.D. Hines, *J Colloid Interface Sci* 180 (2) (1996) 488-492
- [45] J.R. Lu, A. Marrocco, T. Su, R.K. Thomas, J. Penfold, *J Colloid Interface Sci* 158 (2) (1993) 303-316
- [46] K. Medrzycka, W. Zwierzykowski, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 230 (1) (2000) 67-72
- [47] K. Maiti, D. Mitra, S. Guha, S.P. Moulik, *Journal of Molecular Liquids* 146 (1-2) (2009) 44-51
- [48] A. Jakubowska, *J Colloid Interface Sci* 346 (2) (2010) 398-404
- [49] M. Jalali-Heravi, E. Konouz, *J Surfactants Deterg.* 3 (1) (2000) 47-52
- [50] S.L. Yuan, Z.T. Cai, G.Y. Xu, Y.S. Jiang, *J. Dispersion Sci. Technol.* 23 (4) (2002) 465-472
- [51] K. Shinoda, *J. Phys. Chem.* 59 (5) (1955) 432-435